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Impact of Gender on Dry Eye Symptoms After Involutional Ectropion and Entropion Correction Surgery

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Purpose

Lower eyelid malformations, such as ectropion and entropion, significantly affect ocular health and individual well-being. These conditions involve structural alterations to the lower eyelid's position, which may disrupt the eye's normal functioning. Similarly, dry eye syndrome, stemming from insufficiencies in tear production or alterations in tear composition, causes discomfort on the ocular surface and visual disturbances. Although traditionally studied independently, understanding the interplay between these conditions is crucial for comprehensive patient care.

Methods

This prospective case-control study investigated gender-related differences in dry eye symptoms following surgery for involutional ectropion and entropion. A total of 109 patients, aged between 65 and 89, were categorized by eyelid condition and gender. Postoperative assessments included the Tear Film Break-Up Time (TBUT) test, Schirmer I test results, corneal and conjunctival staining, eyelid margin characteristics, and scores from the Ocular Surface Disease Index (OSDI) questionnaire.

Results

The analysis revealed notable gender-related differences in dry eye manifestations. Initially, men exhibited lower TBUT scores but higher Schirmer test readings compared to women; however, these disparities diminished over time. No significant gender differences were detected in corneal and conjunctival staining, indicating similar levels of ocular surface damage across genders. Males showed significantly higher values in several eyelid margin characteristics (LMI, LMT) at various postoperative time points. According to the OSDI questionnaire, women experienced more severe symptoms of dry eye both pre- and post-operatively, suggesting a greater subjective symptom burden.

Conclusion

This study highlights the gender-specific variations in dry eye symptoms following eyelid malformation surgery and emphasizes the importance of adopting gender-sensitive approaches in postoperative care to improve outcomes and ocular health.

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